

TikTok and Marketing Transformation: New Opportunities to Increase Brand Awareness in Promotion of Health System Provider Companies

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Abstract:- TikTok, as a rising social media platform, has become a focal point for many companies in their efforts to increase their brand visibility. This research explores how TikTok has changed the marketing paradigm and introduced new opportunities for health system providers to increase Brand Awareness. This research aims to examine the influence of entertainment, interaction, trends, customization, and electronic word of mouth on Brand Awareness. The population of this study consists of Indonesian people who use the social media TikTok. The sample size for this study was 100 respondents. Questionnaires were used as a sampling method in this research. This type of research is quantitative research. The data obtained was processed using SmartPLS 4.0 software. the findings show that SMM aspects such as entertainment, interaction, trendiness, customization, and electronic word of mouth have a significant impact on brand awareness. The significance of this study is that it will serve as a reference for managers when formulating improvement strategies when formulating marketing strategies to increase brand awareness in companies providing healthcare systems.

Keywords:- TikTok, Digital Marketing, Brand Awareness, Social Media, Health System.

I. INTRODUCTION

Social media has revolutionized the way we interact, share information, and build relationships both personally and professionally. Social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and TikTok have become global communication centers with billions of daily active users and influence many aspects of our lives, including marketing. Over 4.8 billion people around the world use social media platforms, spending an average of 2.5 hours each day (Chaffey, 2021). The role of social media in marketing has grown rapidly. From just being a place to share content to becoming the main tool in marketing strategy. With social media, consumer behavior becomes more comprehensive, it starts with visualizing the consumer's behavior after the purchase without making the purchase, and exchanges information, ideas, and attitudes to make the consumer aware of the presence of social media (Putra & Mudiantono, 2014). Social media's ability to reach a wide audience, convey messages instantly, and build strong engagement makes it a crucial element in promotional efforts for many types of businesses.

TikTok as a social media platform is experiencing an explosion of popularity throughout the world, currently this application has more than 1 billion monthly active users and become one of the fastest growing applications in the world (Iqbal, 2021). Ranked second in the most downloaded Android applications in the world, the results of technological design and cultural conditions make TikTok an application. Children born in the 2010s will definitely enjoy playing with these videos (Bresnick, 2019). TikTok has helped transform the way businesses and brands interact with potential consumers, providing users with new and valuable opportunities to improve their promotions. The appeal of TikTok as a branding tool is further enhanced by the platform guaranteeing at least 5 million ad views per day (Sloane and Rittenhouse, 2019). With features such as short videos, filters, and collaboration between users, the platform allows businesses to create interactive and engaging campaigns that can increase brand awareness.

TikTok has grown exponentially as a very influential platform. Marketing on TikTok has seen tremendous growth over the past few years. According to reports, this social media platform is expected to reach 1.7 billion monthly active users by 2023, making it the best platform for collaboration with brands (Iqbal, 2023). This development provides new opportunities for the healthcare system provider sector that seeks to achieve a higher level of brand awareness. The combination of TikTok videos and music is appealing because users feel like they are directly interacting with the brand being served (Tang, 2019). In addition, the use of intelligent algorithms, and a focus on content that is relevant to users makes TikTok an attractive platform for companies to expand their reach. As an innovative social media platform and can be an effective tool for health system provider companies to increase their brand awareness. Such as through the right marketing campaigns, use of relevant trends, and informative and entertaining content, healthcare companies can leverage TikTok's potential to reach a larger and more diverse audience.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

➤ Brand Awareness

When a brand is in the minds of consumers, it will likely lead to a purchase and ultimately brand loyalty. In addition, if customers are familiar with a brand, they will tend to pay more attention to that brand's advertising compared to other brands they are less familiar with, ultimately increasing the effectiveness of the marketing

campaign. Brand awareness is not just knowledge about a brand and whether consumers have heard of it, but also the physical aspects of the brand, such as logo, brand name, quality, performance, country of origin, and price (Ul Persmacker et al., 2013). Brand awareness pertains to consumers' ability to recall or identify a brand, or their general familiarity with it. In today's digital age, social media significantly influences purchasing choices across different age groups. Brands that actively engage and are frequently discussed by consumers on social platforms tend to have higher visibility among potential buyers compared to those that do not utilize social media to showcase their products (Keller, 2013). Raising familiarity with a brand enables its inclusion in consumer deliberation within a particular category (Langaro, Rita & de Fátima Salgueiro, 2018). Presently, the Internet and Social Media stand as the primary communication avenues significantly shaping customer recognition of brands (Dedeoğlu et al., 2019). The influence of social media on consumers encompasses various actions, including disseminating information, exchanging thoughts and opinions, fostering awareness and comprehension, and envisioning post-buying behaviors without making purchases (Tatar and Erdoğan, 2016).

➤ *Social Media Marketing*

Social Media Marketing involves the strategic use of various social platforms—like social networks, microblogs, and blogs—to create lasting impressions, foster awareness, gain recognition, and prompt engagement for businesses, products, individuals, or brands. It's a method that aims to establish connections, build communities, facilitate transactions, and exchange information with both current consumers and potential customers (Aliami et al., 2018). Social Media Marketing stands as a pivotal factor in establishing brand awareness and profitability among consumers' perceptions (Ashley and Tuten, 2015; Godey et al., 2016; Keller, 2013). Specifically concerning TikTok, SMM involves sharing engaging video content associated with the brand, creating hashtag challenges for the "For You" page, cultivating a community of followers and enthusiasts, and executing promotional activities through advertising. Identified components of SMM encompass entertainment, engagement, following trends, customization, and Electronic Word-of-Mouth (eWOM) (Cheung et al., 2020; Cheung et al., 2021; Kim & Ko, 2012).

➤ *Entertainment*

Entertainment encompasses engaging content crafted by marketers, which audiences find pleasurable, particularly on various social media platforms (Agichtein, Castillo, Donato, Gionis & Mishne, 2008). Brands leverage entertainment to foster and reinforce a sense of connection with consumers, influencing their inclination towards making purchases (Dessart Veloutsou, & Morgan-Thomas, 2015). Entertainment is considered capable of strengthening the intentions of consumers to make purchases can be influenced, fostering a deeper connection between the consumer and the brand. This connection can be strengthened through entertaining activities like gaming, active participation, and sharing of videos that can make consumers enjoy their experience on social media more, so that this can motivate

their participation in a brand community and pay more attention to the brand because they feel there is a bond built through content. created by the brand (Ashley & Tuten, 2015; Kaye, 2007; Liu & Arnett, 2000; Manthiou et al., 2013). In TikTok content, it is important to create entertaining content so that users watch the video until the end and do not immediately move on to other content (Gummerus, Liljander, Wemanand Pihlström, 2012). Engaging content boosts audience engagement and enhances the potential for online content to become widely shared (Golan & Zaidner, 2008). This phenomenon is observable on platforms like TikTok through metrics such as likes, comments, and shares.

- *H1: Entertainment has a significant effect on Brand Awareness.*

➤ *Interaction*

Interaction in social media denotes the level at which platforms allow for the sharing of information and the exchange of thoughts and viewpoints in a bidirectional manner (Muntinga et al., 2011). Through the strategic dissemination of content tailored to their audience, social media users can stimulate conversations and foster stronger connections between consumers and brands (Cheung, Pires, & Rosenberger, 2020). Leveraging TikTok as a platform for posting content promotes consumer engagement, thereby enhancing a brand's presence in the minds of consumers. This is evident in the comment section, which serves as a space for users to engage in discussions with one another.

- *H2: Interaction has a significant effect on Brand Awareness.*

➤ *Trendiness*

Trendiness pertains to the way social media offers up-to-date discussions and popular topics. People are often driven to seek out current information about a brand on social platforms, which prompts them to stay updated with the brand's latest happenings by exploring relevant trends (Gallagher & Ransbotham, 2010). This approach proves beneficial for business professionals aiming to furnish consumers with up-to-date and popular information, streamlining the consumer's search process by providing readily available content (Becker et al., 2011; Laroche et al., 2013). Current and popular information plays a pivotal role in capturing consumer attention, fostering positive consumer sentiments, and fostering brand loyalty (Liu, Shin, & Burns, 2021). Achieving traction on platforms like TikTok involves consistently updating brand-related information in sync with ongoing trends. Identifying and aligning with prevalent topics is crucial in maintaining brand integrity (Budak et al., 2011). The more current the topic, the higher the likelihood of piquing consumer interest in the brand (Cheung et al., 2021).

- *H3: Trendiness has a significant effect on Brand Awareness.*

➤ *Customization*

Customization refers to efforts to satisfy consumers' personal preferences to the extent of customizing a service, message, and marketing effort (Godey et al., 2016). Customization can encompass marketing strategies aimed at delivering personalized satisfaction to consumers. This involves tailoring services to individual preferences and ensuring easy access to information, ultimately adding value for consumers (Cheung et al., 2020). On TikTok, customized messages can be found on content pages that post videos containing specific tips or information. Customization can additionally empower brands to stay in touch with their audience and converse about subjects linked to their brand identity, ultimately encouraging consumers to interact with the brand (Cheung et al., 2021).

- *H4: Customization has a significant effect on Brand Awareness.*

➤ *Electronic Word Of Mouth (eWOM)*

Electronic Word of Mouth (eWOM) refers to the exchange of information among potential or current users of a brand. It encompasses how consumers engage on social media platforms, sharing their experiences and opinions to inform others about the brand. This communication involves posting on personal blogs, sharing thoughts, and interacting with others (Cheung et al., 2020). The level of eWOM is gauged by how extensively consumers disseminate, exchange, and upload information through social media channels (Kudeshia & Kumar, 2017). On platforms like TikTok, eWOM activities manifest through users creating videos evaluating products, commenting on brands, sharing brand-related TikTok content with their followers, and conducting unboxings or reviews. These activities hold immense significance, with over 70% of consumers placing trust in user comments on social media, surpassing trust in traditional marketing efforts (Hollebeek, Srivastava & Chen, 2019).

- *H5: Entertainment has a significant effect on Brand Awareness.*

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This research was conducted with a quantitative approach using statistical procedures to determine the influence of the relationship between entertainment, interaction, trends, customization, eWOM on Brand Awareness. The subjects and population of this study were TikTok social media users over 17 years old with a total of 100 respondents. The process of gathering information involved the utilization of a questionnaire distributed via Google Forms to participants. The questionnaire employed a 5-point Likert scale for responses, ranging from 1 for 'strongly disagree' to 5 for 'strongly agree' (Kim and Ko, 2012). A total of 24 measurement items were employed to assess various aspects of Social Media Marketing (SMM) including Entertainment, Interaction, Trendiness, Customization, and eWOM. These measurement items were utilized to evaluate how SMM dimensions impact brand awareness (Kim and Hyun, 2011). To test the hypothesis used, the Partial Least Square (PLS) analysis technique was used, then the collected data was processed using Smart PLS 4.0.

Table 1 Characteristics Respondents

Items	Classifications	Number of People
Gender	Man	25
	Woman	75
Ages	17-25 years	70
	26-35 years	15
	36-45 years	10
	46-55 years	5
Job	Student	52
	Private employees	21
	Freelancer	9
	Entrepreneur	7
	Other	11

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 Loading Factor

Variabel	Indikator	Outer Loading
Entertainment (X1)	X1.1	0.777
	X1.2	0.848
	X1.3	0.712
	X1.4	0.612
Interaction (X2)	X2.1	0.661
	X2.2	0.822
	X2.3	0.602
	X2.4	0.830
Trendiness (X3)	X3.1	0.710
	X3.2	0.835
	X3.3	0.824
	X3.4	0.816

Customization (X4)	X4.1	0.812
	X4.2	0.851
	X4.3	0.843
	X4.4	0.761
eWOM (X5)	X5.1	0.835
	X5.2	0.721
	X5.3	0.777
	X5.4	0.718
Brand Awareness (Y1)	Y1.1	0.753
	Y1.2	0.850
	Y1.3	0.796
	Y1.4	0.764

For indicator reliability, it will be said to be reliable if the outer loading value is above 0.4 (Hair, 2011). The outcomes of the processing demonstrate that every measure has factor loading values exceeding 0.4, indicating their reliability.

Table 3 Average variance extracted (AVE) & Composite reliability

Variabel	Average variance extracted (AVE)	Composite reliability
Entertainment (X1)	0.551	0.745
Interaction (X2)	0.541	0.717
Trendiness (X3)	0.636	0.816
Customization (X4)	0.669	0.838
eWOM (X5)	0.584	0.768
Brand Awareness (Y1)	0.627	0.801

The processing results of all variables are declared valid and reliable with a standard Average Variance Extracted of more than 0.5 and a value for Composite Reliability of more than 0.7 (Amir, 2020).

Fig 1 Research Model Results

Table 4 Path Coefficient

Variabel	P values
Entertainment -> Brand Awareness	0.049
Interaction -> Brand Awareness	0.031
Trendiness -> Brand Awareness	0.006
Customization -> Brand Awareness	0.003
eWOM -> Brand Awareness	0.017

The analysis findings indicate that entertainment, interaction, trendiness, customization, and eWOM all exhibit statistically significant impacts on Brand Awareness. Specifically, entertainment (p=0.049), interaction (p=0.031), trendiness (p=0.006), customization (p=0.003), and eWOM (p=0.017) were found to have p-values below the threshold of 0.05, confirming their noteworthy influence on Brand Awareness.

V. CONCLUSION

The study findings indicate that the five ideas—entertainment, interaction, trendiness, customization, and eWOM (electronic Word-of-Mouth)—strongly impact Brand Awareness according to the research. This indicates that these aspects play an important role in increasing brand awareness among consumers. Entertainment, with its ability to entertain and attract attention, as well as active interaction between brands and consumers, appears to be a contributing factor to increased brand awareness. Apart from that, trendiness and the ability to adapt to consumer needs or customization also

have a significant impact on brand awareness. Lastly, eWOM or electronic recommendations from individuals or other users have also been shown to positively influence brand awareness. This conclusion highlights the importance of these factors in building strong brand awareness and attracting consumer attention in today's marketing environment and can be used as a reference in the Promotion of Health System Provider Companies

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